

FATIGUE LIFE OF POST-BUCKLED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue life prediction of post-buckled composite structures represents still an unresolved issue due to the complexity of the phenomenon and the high costs of experimental testing. In this paper, a novel numerical approach, called “Min-Max Load Approach” is adopted to analyze the behavior of a single-stringer composite specimen with an initial delamination subjected to post-buckling fatigue compressive load. The proposed approach, based on cohesive zone model technique, is able to evaluate the local stress ratio during the delamination growth, performing, in a single finite element analysis, the simulation of the structure at the maximum and minimum load of the fatigue cycle. The knowledge of the actual value of the local stress ratio is crucial to correctly calculate the crack growth rate. At first, the specimen is analyzed under quasi-static loading conditions, then, the fatigue simulation is performed. The outcomes of the numerical analysis are compared with the data of an experimental campaign previously conducted.

1 INTRODUCTION

The potentialities of composite structures in the aerospace industry have not yet been fully exploited, especially in the post-buckling regime, due to the difficulties in controlling and predicting their complex failure mechanisms. Indeed, typical aeronautical composite stiffened panels can safely work in the post-buckling regime, but their collapse mode is quite complex, as it is due to the interaction of the post-buckling deformation with different failure modes, such as intralaminar damage, delamination, skin-stringer separation. The phenomenon is even more complex for fatigue loading conditions, due to the interaction between the geometric nonlinearity of the response, the different possible damage modes, and the accumulation of cyclic damage.

Delamination, and in particular skin-stringer separations, are among the most critical types of damage in stiffened panels, as they can rapidly grow under service loading condition, leading to the sudden collapse of the structure.

Despite the large number of studies, the simulation of interlaminar damage in composite structures subjected to fatigue load is still an open question. Delamination growth is usually treated as a crack propagation problem, and most of the existing numerical approaches make use of methodologies originated for metallic material, such as the Paris law [1]. In the last decades, a variety of numerical techniques have been developed with the aim to integrate the Paris law in the framework of a Finite Element (FE) analysis. Cohesive zone models have been widely used to simulate delamination in composite laminates subjected to static or impact loads [2], and recently have been extended by some authors to take into account degradation due to cyclic load by incorporating the Paris law within the cohesive constitutive model [3-5].

The main objective of the proposed fatigue approach is to develop a high-fidelity validated methodology, based on FE method and on Cohesive Zone Model (CZM), able to predict the propagation of fatigue damage in post-buckled composite structures. In particular, single-stringer specimens are studied, as they are relatively small, computationally tractable yet detailed damage models can be constructed to account for all damage modes of corresponding multi-stringer panels [6-8].

The methodology under development focuses on three different but connected aspects of fatigue: the correct evaluation of the local stress ratio, the implementation of a damage constitutive model and the definition of a fatigue damage initiation criterion.

In this paper, the numerical approach, developed to correctly evaluate the local stress ratio during a fatigue crack propagation analysis, is applied to a single-stringer specimen and the numerical results are compared to experimental data previously obtained.

2 MIN-MAX LOAD APPROACH

A numerical approach, called “Min-Max Load Approach” [9], has been developed to evaluate during a fatigue analysis, the local stress ratio, that is the ratio between the minimum and the maximum stress at the crack tip. Indeed, the crack propagation rate is highly dependent on the local stress ratio, which may not be equal to the applied load ratio, that is the ratio between the minimum and the maximum value of the applied load during the fatigue cycle. This can happen, for example, when the structure is subjected to two or more non-synchronized loads or when stiffened structures are tested in post-buckling conditions, where the buckling mode shape may change between the minimum and maximum load of the fatigue cycle.

In the developed approach, two models representing the same structure but with different applied loads are analyzed in a single simulation. One model simulates the deformed shape of the structure when the applied load is equal to the minimum value of the fatigue cycle, and the other one represents the deformed configuration of the specimen at the maximum load. The two models exchange information between each other to evaluate the local stress ratio and perform the fatigue calculation. The approach, applied to a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) is illustrated in Fig. 1. The fatigue damage calculation is based on the constitutive model of the cohesive interface proposed by Turon et al. [3] and on the semi-empirical fatigue delamination growth law presented by Allegri et al. [10].

Figure 1: Min-Max Load Approach applied to a Double Cantilever Beam.

The “Min-Max Load Approach” has been implemented inside the FE code ABAQUS using a User Material Subroutine (UMAT) [11], which allows to define a completely user-defined material behavior and to share the information between the two models. The methodology has been validated in [9] for fatigue crack propagation under pure mode I and mixed-mode conditions performing numerical simulations on DCB and Mixed Mode Bending (MMB) tests, and comparing the results with data tests taken from literature [12-14]. The “Min-Max Load Approach” has been then adopted to analyze a specimen similar to the MMB but with modified boundary conditions such as to produce a variable local stress ratio different from the applied load ratio [9]. The results have demonstrated that the approach is able to evaluate the local stress ratio during the delamination propagation allowing to properly modifying the Paris law parameters according to the actual value of the stress ratio.

In this work, the developed numerical approach is adopted to simulate the propagation of skin-stringer separation in an aeronautical stiffened panel under compressive fatigue loads. In particular, the Single-Stringer Compression (SSC) specimen, designed and tested in [6-8], is analyzed.

3 SINGLE-STRINGER COMPRESSION SPECIMEN

The SSC specimen has been designed to capture the behavior of large multi-stringer panels, typical of fuselage structures. Despite its small size, the specimen displays a relative high level of complexity, allowing the study of failure behavior in post-buckling regime and providing data to verify quasi-static and fatigue numerical models thanks to its limited dimensions which make it computationally feasible.

The SSC specimen consists in a skin co-cured with an omega-shaped stringer. An initial delamination has been induced in the center of the specimen using a Teflon film inserted between the skin and the stringer flange. The geometrical characteristics of the specimen are displayed in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Single-stringer compression specimen: geometry.

The skin is made of 8 plies of carbon-epoxy IM7/8552 with the stacking sequence $[45/90/-45/0]_s$, while the stringer has 7 plies with the layup $[-45/0/45/0/45/0/-45]$. The material properties adopted in the numerical analyses are shown in Table 1.

Lamina properties			Interface properties		
E_1	[MPa]	150000	G_{1C}	[kJ/m ²]	0.277
$E_2 = E_3$	[MPa]	9080	G_{2C}	[kJ/m ²]	0.788
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	[MPa]	5290	η		1.63
G_{23}	[MPa]	3900			
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$		0.32			
ν_{23}		0.45			

Table 1: IM7/8552 material properties [8].

The SSC specimen is discretized in the FE code ABAQUS [11] using continuum shell elements (SC8R) with a size of approximately 2 mm. A layer of zero-thickness cohesive elements (COH3D8) is placed between the skin and the stringer flange where the damage is located. In this region and, in particular, in the areas potentially interested by the delamination growth, a finer discretization is adopted with an element length of 0.05 mm in the propagation direction. To reduce the total number of elements and decrease the computational times, the stringer flange and the portion of the skin below it are connected to the surrounding part of the structure using tie constraints.

Two references points, one at each ends of the specimen, are defined and rigidly connected to the nodes located on the edges to uniformly apply the load. All the degrees of freedom are blocked to the reference point on the encased end of the specimen, while on the opposite end the specimen is allowed

to move only along the longitudinal axis. The potting is numerically simulated constraining the lateral and out-of-plane displacements of the nodes and allowing them to move along the axial direction. The details of FE model and boundary conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Single-stringer compression specimen: finite element model and boundary conditions.

The nodal coordinates of the model are perturbed using the displacements obtained from an eigenvalue buckling analysis. The displacements are scaled to 1% of their values and added to the nodal coordinates to promote a smoothly transition through the buckling bifurcation point and to avoid convergence issues.

At first, a quasi-static analysis is performed applying a compressive load to the reference point. The force versus displacement curve is presented in Fig. 4 and compared with the experimental data [7].

Figure 4: Quasi-static load-displacement curves.

The trend of the numerical results in Fig.4 is similar to the experimental data, although the predicted stiffness is higher and the maximum load is lower. These differences may be due to a combination of multiple factors, such as the geometrical imperfections of the test specimens, the alignment of the loaded surfaces or the boundary conditions assumed for the potting. Furthermore, the interface properties adopted in the numerical analysis are experimentally evaluated using simple specimens such as DCB or MMB with delamination positioned between 0° plies, while, in the tested specimen, the skin-stringer separation is located between 0° and 45° plies, resulting in much higher values of fracture toughness.

In the numerical analysis the skin-stringer separation starts to propagate around an applied load of 18.5 kN, as it can be seen from the stiffness variation in the graph in Fig. 4, and rapidly grows up to 20 kN when the delamination reaches the boundary of the finer cohesive elements area and the analysis is terminated. The experimental fatigue tests in [8] were conducted cycling the specimen between 2.3 kN and 23 kN, however, the same load cycle cannot be adopted in the numerical analysis otherwise the maximum load would exceed the numerical ultimate load resulting in a complete separation of the skin from the stringer in the first load cycle. For this reason, the numerical fatigue analysis is performed with a maximum load of 18 kN, right before the beginning of the unstable propagation, and an applied load ratio of 0.1.

The “Min-Max Load Approach” is implemented discretizing two identical models of the SSC specimen, representative of the specimen subjected to the maximum and to the minimum load during the fatigue cycle. In Fig. 5 the deformed shapes in the two configurations are shown at the beginning of the fatigue analysis.

Figure 5: Deformed shape of the maximum and minimum load models.

The specimen oscillates between pre- and post-buckling conditions in each load cycle. During the simulation, as the skin-stringer separation advances, the out-of-plane displacements increase and the specimen jumps through different buckling modes. The deformed shapes of the maximum load configuration with the out-of-plane displacements contour plot are shown in Fig. 6 at different load cycles.

Figure 6: Deformed shape at maximum load for different load cycles.

Initially, the skin buckles in three half-wave mode on both sides of the specimen, as expected considering the initial imperfection applied to the model. After about 7800 cycles the portion of the skin on the opposite side of the delamination reverses its buckling direction, while beneath the delamination the skin starts to shift into a single half-wave mode. Finally, around 8100 cycles the growth of the separation between skin and stringer causes the stringer flange to snap from a single half-wave mode to a two half-wave buckling mode.

The propagation of the separation is clearly affected by the sequence of buckling events, which themselves are influenced by the growth of the delamination. In Fig. 7 the evolution of the separation is presented at different load cycles.

Figure 7: Delamination front at different load cycles.

The separation grows slowly in the first 7000 cycles, then, the changes in the buckling mode shape leads to an increase in the crack growth rate. The analysis is terminated after 10000 cycles because at that point, one of the separation fronts has reached the end of the refined cohesive zone.

Comparisons in terms of deformed shape and delamination length with experimental digital image correlation data and ultrasonic scan are reported in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively.

MIN-MAX LOAD APPROACH

10000 Cycles

EXPERIMENTAL

11850 Cycles

Figure 8: Comparison between numerical and experimental out-of-plane displacements.

Figure 9: Comparison between numerical and experimental damage propagation.

In Fig.8 the numerical out-of-plane displacement distribution can be qualitatively compared to the experimental data, showing an excellent agreement in terms of buckling mode shape. The final length of the skin-stringer separation predicted by the numerical simulation, shown in Fig. 9, is comparable with the value measured experimentally both in terms of size and number of cycles.

However, it has to be taken into account that the numerical analysis is performed at a lower maximum load respect to the experimental test. Experimental data are needed to characterize the interface between the skin and the stringer for quasi-static and fatigue delamination propagation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the behavior of a single-stringer composite specimen with an initial delamination subjected to post-buckling compressive fatigue load has been numerically investigated using an innovative approach. The methodology, in a single finite elements analysis, simulates the structure at the maximum and minimum load of the fatigue cycle, allowing to capture the actual value of the local stress ratio. The results of the numerical analysis have proven to be consistent with the data obtained from an experimental campaign previously performed, showing the potentialities of the proposed approach, although the numerical simulation has been conducted at a lower maximum load. Indeed, further experimental data are required to correctly characterize the quasi-static and fatigue damage propagation of the considered interface.

The work is under development to estimate the fatigue crack propagation by an approach based on the S-N diagrams, and then initiation criteria in composite structures due to fatigue load will be investigated. The methodology will contribute to the development of a numerical tool able to reduce the number of tests required for the design and certification of structures in composite materials.

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